

**Þróun á vinnsluferli til fullnýtingar á klóþangi
(*Ascophyllum nodosum*) úr Breiðafirði**

Sophie Jensen
Cécile Dargentolle
Rósa Jónsdóttir

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<i>Titill / Title</i>	Próun á vinnsluferli til fullnýtingar á klóþangi (<i>Ascophyllum nodosum</i>) úr Breiðafirði		
<i>Höfundar / Authors</i>	Sophie Jensen, Cécile Dargentolle, Rósa Jónsdóttir		
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<i>Ágríp á íslensku:</i>	Markmið þessa verkefnis var að draga út og rannsaka verðmæt innihaldsefni, fucoxanthin, alginöt og fucoïdan, úr hrati, þ.e. því sem fellur til við framleiðslu á plöntulíförva úr klóþangi, sem hægt er að nýta í fæðubótarefni eða matvæli. Með þessu móti voru kannaðir möguleikar á fullnýtingu lífmassans og þar með mikilli verðmætaaukningu.		
<i>Lykilorð á íslensku:</i>	<i>Klóþang, raðbundinn útdráttur, fullnýting</i>		

<p><i>Summary in English:</i></p>	<p>The aim of this project was to extract and study valuable ingredients, fucoxanthin, alginates and fucoidan, from the residue biomass from the production of biostimulant from <i>Ascophyllum nodosum</i>, which can be used in dietary supplements or food. In this way, the possibilities were explored to fully utilise the seaweed biomass and thereby greatly increasing its value.</p>
<p><i>English keywords:</i></p>	<p><i>Ascophyllum nodosum, sequential extraction, full utilisation</i></p>

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Introduction

Background and historical use of *Ascophyllum nodosum* in Iceland

Ascophyllum nodosum, commonly known as knotted wrack or klóþang in Icelandic, has been utilised in Iceland for centuries. Until the early 20th century, its primary use was as fuel for cooking and heating. In 1975, commercial harvesting and production of seaweed meal began in Reykhólar, located by Breiðafjörður, marking the start of continuous exploitation of this seaweed in the region. Over the past two decades, annual harvests have ranged between 15 000 and 20 000 tonnes. A study performed by the Icelandic Marine and Freshwater Research Institute in 2019, estimated the total biomass of *A. nodosum* in Breiðafjörður at 1.06 and 1.37 million tonnes and recommended a sustainable harvest limit of 40 000 tonnes per year [1].

Global and local interest in seaweed processing and utilisation

A growing interest in expanding seaweed utilisation in Breiðafjörður reflects the global trend of increased attention to seaweed as a sustainable resource. Breiðafjörður is known for its prolific seaweed growth and unique tidal dynamics. In Iceland, Canada, and Ireland, brown seaweeds, including *A. nodosum*, have primarily been processed into seaweed meal. This involves harvesting wild biomass, chopping, drying, milling, sieving, and packaging. Most of the meal is exported and used for alginate extraction, fertilizer, or animal feed. However, biostimulant production from *A. nodosum* has grown significantly in recent years. The EU Blue Economy Report (2022) [2] notes that 15% of European macroalgae biomass goes to supplements, 17% to cosmetics, and 11% to fertilizers and biostimulants.

Bioactive compounds, health potential and market potential

Seaweeds are rich sources of biologically active compounds, including pigments, polysaccharides (especially dietary fibres), polyphenols, and polyunsaturated fatty acids. These compounds exhibit potential health benefits, prompting increased interest among scientists and the food industry. One promising avenue is the extraction of bioactive compounds for use in functional foods and dietary supplements, such as the antioxidants fucoxanthin and fucoidan. Fucoxanthin is a seaweed-specific xanthophyll carotenoid responsible for the brown colour of macroalgae. It exhibits strong antioxidant activity and may protect against inflammation-related diseases [3-8]. Ethanol is an effective solvent for fucoxanthin extraction, and studies have explored various ethanol ratios and process

variables. Fucoxanthin concentrations have been reported in different brown seaweed species [4]: *Laminaria digitata*: 0.65–1.4 mg/g dry weight, *Alaria esculenta*: 0.8–0.9 mg/g, *Fucus vesiculosus*: 0.7 mg/g, *Ascophyllum nodosum*: 0.02-0.5 mg/g [9].

Fucoidan refers to a group of sulphated polysaccharides rich in L-fucose, primarily extracted from brown seaweeds. Their molecular weights range from 10 to 10 000 kDa. Fucoidans have been extensively studied for their biological activity and potential in pharmaceuticals and functional foods. Fucoxanthin and fucoidan are not currently produced in Iceland, despite their high value and proven bioactivity. Algalf in Iceland is expecting a fucoxanthin product isolated from the microalgae *Phaeodactylum tricornutum* to become commercially available in the near future [10].

Biostimulant production

Biostimulant provides slow and sustained nutrient release by retaining nutrients in the root zone, allowing plants to absorb them as needed. This supports natural nutrient cycling and improves fertilizer efficiency. Additionally, it enhances mineral availability in soil, boosts biological activity, and improves soil quality, fertility, and structure which are all vital for healthy plants and animals. Although Iceland has not previously produced biostimulants from seaweed, such products are made abroad using Icelandic *A. nodosum*. Ultrasound-assisted extraction (UAE) is defined as a technique that employs ultrasound waves to disrupt cell walls and facilitates the release of bioactive compounds into a solvent. This method can be applied to finely milled seaweed, to produce a liquid concentrate that enhances plant growth by improving nutrient retention and soil health [11].

Potential in residual biomass

The residue seaweed biomass from biostimulant production, can contain valuable compounds such as fucoxanthin, alginate, and fucoidan which can be extracted and used for food, supplements, and cosmetics, aligning with circular economy principles. Alginate yields from seaweed range from 17% to 40%, depending on species, season, and extraction method [12-14]. Producing 23 000 tonnes of alginate requires approximately 85 000 tonnes of dried seaweed. Industrial-scale processing generates substantial residue, often discarded or minimally reused, meaning up to 70% of dried biomass remains underutilised [15-17]. Post-alginate extraction residues still contain valuable compounds such as fucoxanthin, cellulose,

and fucoidan [18-20] which are often overlooked. Improved processing, including additional extraction steps, could recover these compounds, reduce waste, and enhance product value.

Innovation in seaweed-based enterprises in Iceland remains in early stages. While seaweed meal has been produced for years, it is mostly exported for further processing and despite promising research, Iceland has struggled to translate innovation into commercial success.

The primary goal of this project was to extract and analyse high-value compounds such as fucoxanthin, alginate, and fucoidan from the residual seaweed biomass generated during biostimulant production. Building on the foundation to explore full biomass utilisation, reduce waste and create value by developing high-value products for the food, cosmetics, biomedical, and aquaculture industries. The long-term goal is to establish a tiered valorisation model that transforms all raw materials and side streams into marketable outputs while supporting sustainable marine resource utilisation.

Material and Methods

Seaweed samples and processing

Ascophyllum nodosum harvested in Breiðafjörður by ISEA, using their harvesting barge. The seaweed was dried and grinded by ISEA in Stykkishólmur and then transported to Matís in 25 kg brown paper bags. The following *A. nodosum* samples were investigated:

	Aug-2024	Dec-2024	July-2025
Drying method	65°C	Cold vacuum	Cold vacuum
Particle size	0.8-2.0 mm	<0.25 mm	<3 mm

Biostimulant extraction

The biostimulant extraction was initially conducted using a laboratory scale probe (4210 probe combined with a Qsonica interface, both provided by Qsonicators, Newtown USA) on small amounts of sample (with approximately 80 g of dry grinded seaweed material of particle size between 0.8 and 2mm). Ultrasound was applied using different water:dry material ratios and different power settings (watt), amplitude was set to 80%. The different parameters and settings tested are summarised in Table 1. During the scale up trials, a probe (UIP2000hdT) and interface (IP20RoHS) from Hielscher ultrasound technology were used.

Table 1. Parameters and settings tested during biostimulant extraction at laboratory scale. Probe used was 4210 and the amplitude was set to 80%.

Parameters	Settings		
Ratio (seaweed:water)	1:5	1:10	1:10
Dry mass (g)	83	83	80
Water volume (mL)	400	800	800
Total duration (min)	15	15	20
Pulse	1 s on / 2 s off	1 s on / 2 s off	None
Power (W)	130-140	150-160	130-140
Total energy (J)	30 000	35 000	45 000

After the ultrasound treatment, the samples were centrifuged at 4000 rcf/g for 10 min at 21°C and the supernatant (biostimulant) was separated from the pellet (used for subsequent extraction). The water content of both supernatant and pellet were measured.

After testing the extraction at laboratory scale, it was decided to perform extraction at a larger scale to evaluate how scale-up processes can be done and if it would be as efficient compared

to when done at laboratory scale. The scale up (Table 2) was done mainly to evaluate the influence of particle size, season of harvesting and duration of processing.

Table 2. Parameters and settings tested during biostimulant extraction at small pilot scale. Process done with the ultrasound probe from Hielscher Technology.

Parameters	Settings		
Particle size (mm)	<0.25	0.8-2	<3
Season	Dec 2024	Aug 2024	Jul 2025
Ratio (seaweed:water)	1:8		
Total duration (min)	20		
Pulse (min)	1	10	5
Power (W)	1800		
Amplitude (%)	100		

Fucoxanthin extraction

Extraction solvents were either pure ethanol, methanol or 70% ethanol in water (H₂O). Extraction methods applied were sonication at 45°C in a sonication bath for 20 minutes or with the similar Qsonica probe at around 140 W for 20 min (1 min on-30s off), or at pilot scale with the Hielscher ultrasound probe at 1800 W, amplitude 100%, for 20 min (1 min on-30s off) with a ratio 1:10 (dry seaweed:ethanol). When using the Hielscher ultrasound probe, when the temperature was reaching 50°C, the sonication was paused, and the mix was cooled down on ice until the temperature reached around 30°C before starting again. The use of a sonication bath instead of the probe was also tested at 45°C for 20 min in a 2 L flask before filtering through a 50 µm nylon filter. The solvent was evaporated with a rotary evaporator to obtain a dry extract. The extract was analysed by HPLC for fucoxanthin content.

Fucoidan extraction

Dry biomass (40 g), residue after fucoxanthin extraction from the 0.8-2.5mm samples treated with the ultrasound probe during the fucoxanthin extraction, was suspended in 1 L of either 0.1M or 0.2M hydrochloric acid (HCl) and shaken on an IKA HS 360 basic shaker for 2 hours. The liquid was separated from the seaweed material by filtration through a 50 µm nylon filter. The supernatant was neutralised with sodium hydroxide (NaOH) before freeze drying and extraction yield recorded. The extract was analysed for monosaccharide composition, salt and protein content.

Alginate extraction

Alginate was extracted from the residue biomass after fucoidan extraction applying a sodium alginate process. The residue was resuspended in 1 L of H₂O and shaken for 1 hour then filtered and supernatant was discharged. The filtrate was resuspended in 1.5 L of 0.1M sodium bicarbonate (NaHCO₃) and incubated for 2 hours before adjusting pH to 8, using NaOH, and then stirring overnight on an IKA HS 360 basic shaker. Supernatant was recovered by filtration through a 50 µm nylon filter. The residue was resuspended in H₂O and pH adjusted to >7 and shaken for 2 hours before filtering again and recovering the supernatant. The extraction in H₂O was repeated 3 times, producing 4 supernatants that were combined into a total final volume of approximately 3 L of liquid containing dissolved alginates. To recover the alginates, sodium chloride (NaCl) was dissolved in a small volume of H₂O and thoroughly mixed in the supernatants, assuring 0.2% (w/v). Then pure ethanol was added in a 1:2 (v/v) ratio to precipitate the sodium alginate which was filtered out through a 20-micron nylon filter. The alginates were washed with ethanol and last acetone and then dried in an oven at low heat over night, weighed and extraction yield recorded. The final product was analysed for monosaccharide composition.

Cellulose extraction

Cellulose was extracted using two different methods. First, a method used at Matís before was tested, where the seaweed residue was mixed with 1.4% sodium chlorite (NaClO₂) at a ratio of 0.6% to 1.2% of dry material in the solution. The pH was then adjusted to 3 with pure acetic acid and the solution heated at 70°C for 5h with stirring. After this step, the residue was cleaned and rinsed with distilled water and a 0.1M NaOH solution until the pH was back to above 6.

Since sodium chlorite is a hazardous chemical, it was decided to test as well, greener options for the cellulose extraction. Since the samples have already been somewhat processed, the cellulose extraction might be accomplished using less harsh chemicals. It was decided to test hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) to extract cellulose. A 32% hydrogen peroxide solution was prepared and mixed at a ratio 1:10 of dry raw material against hydrogen peroxide and heated at 80°C for 5 hours.

Chemical analysis

Fucoxanthin analysis

Fucoxanthin was analysed using a ThermoFisher Scientific (USA) Ultimate 3000 UHPLC Series liquid chromatograph equipped with a degasser, a binary pump, an autosampler, a column oven and coupled to a Thermo Scientific Dionex Ultimate DAD-3000 measuring absorbance at 450 and 242 nm. Chromatographic separation was obtained using a Kromaphase C18 column (4.6 x 250 mm, 5 μ m, 100 Å, Scharlau, Barcelona) with mobile phases (A): Milli-Q H₂O and (B): methanol (VWR hypergrade) and the following gradient program:

Time (min)	Mobile phase A (%)	Mobile phase B (%)
0.00	20	80
15.00	0	100
17.00	0	100
17.10	20	80
22.00	20	80

The flow rate was 1.2 mL/min, and the injection volume was 10 μ L. Mobile phases were sonicated for 15 min before use. The total acquisition lasted 22 minutes.

The calibration curve ranged between 1–20 μ g/mL. The analyte fucoxanthin (1 mg) was purchased as analytical standard (>95%) from Supelco and a stock solution (2 mg/mL) prepared in ethanol and kept at -20°C. The stock solution was allowed to reach ambient temperature and sonicated for app 1 min before use. From the stock solution a working solution (50 μ g/mL) was prepared by diluting 50 μ L of stock solution in 1.95 mL of methanol. Calibration curve levels were diluted directly from the working solution. The extracts were dissolved in methanol at a concentration of 10 mg/mL before analysis on HPLC.

Monosaccharide and uronic acid analysis

Samples were prepared according to the official NREL (National Renewable Energy Laboratory) method for determination of total carbohydrates in algal biomass laboratory analytical procedure (NREL, 2013). An aliquot of hydrolysed seaweed extract (1–3 mL) was neutralised to a pH between 6 and 8 using 1M calcium carbonate solution and centrifuged in 5 mL tubes (Sarstedt, ref. 60.558.001) in TS 5.1–500 rotor (Beckman Coulter TJ-25 centrifuge, Germany) at 5530 *g* for 10 min. Supernatants were filtered through 0.45 μ m syringe filter and diluted with Milli-Q water. Samples were analysed on a Dionex ICS 5000+ (Thermo Scientific, USA) with HPAE-PAD detection. Column used was a Dionex Carbo Pack PA 20 (3 \times 150 mm) (Thermo Scientific, USA). Injection volume was 10 μ L. Temperature was 30°C. The system was

set up with a gold working electrode and a silver/silver chloride reference electrode. Eluent composition was A: 200 mM NaOH, B: 1M sodium acetate (CH₃COONa) in 200 mM NaOH and C: Milli-Q water. Reference standards for the monosaccharides were mannitol, fucose, galactose, glucose and xylose. Reference standards for uronic acids were guluronic acid and mannuronic acid. The following gradient programmes were used:

Gradient for monosaccharide analysis. Flow rate: 0.5 mL/min.

Time (min)	Mobile phase A (%)	Mobile phase C (%)	Gradient step
-15	5	95	Equilibration
0-14	5	95	Run
14	100	0	
21	100	0	Stop

Gradient for uronic acid analysis. Flow rate: 0.4 mL/min.

Time (min)	A (%)	B (%)	C (%)	Gradient step
-20	1.2		98.8	Equilibration
0-20	1.2		98.8	Run
20-30	50		50	
30-36.1	20	30	50	
36.1		50	50	
50		50	50	Stop

Protein analysis

The method used for protein analysis is the accredited method from Dumas – ISO 16634-1-2008 (E), performed at the accredited laboratory at Matís. Briefly, the samples were grinded, sieved to obtain a homogeneous sample, which is then combusted through the Dumas apparatus and the total nitrogen content is compared to a known sample.

Salt (NaCl) analysis

The method used for the sodium analysis is an accredited modified NMKL (Nordic Committee on Food Analysis) 186 (2007) method and was performed at the accredited laboratory at Matís (method SV-22-02-SN-1 in Matis Quality manual). Briefly, up to 200 (±0.1) mg of samples weighed and transferred to digestion vessels together with 1 mL nitric acid (HNO₃) and 1 mL H₂O₂. Samples were digested in a Milestone Ultrawave Acid Digestion System (Milestone Inc., USA). Trace elements in the digests were determined by ICP-MS (Agilent 7900, Waldbronn, Germany), using ¹¹⁵In as internal standard.

Water analysis

The water content of both the biostimulant and the rest raw materials after each extraction was analysed with the ISO 6496-1999 method. Briefly, between 2 to 5 g of sample was accurately weighed on a precision scale. The sample was put in a 102°C oven for a minimum of 4 hours, and then for 30 minutes in a desiccator, before weighed again. The water content was calculated as the percentage of weight loss during the time spent in the oven.

Antioxidant analysis

Total polyphenol content (TPC)

The Folin-Ciocalteu assay was used to analyse the TPC in the different seaweed extracts. TPC was determined according to the method by Singleton and Rossi (1965) [21] adapted to microplate format and some modifications. Seven concentrations (0–100 µg/mL) of gallic acid (Sigma, cat. no. G7384) and phloroglucinol (Sigma, cat. no. 79330) were used to create standard curves. Results were calculated both as gram of phloroglucinol equivalents (PGE) per 100 g sample and gallic acid equivalent (GAE) per 100 g sample using interpolation from regression analysis.

DPPH (2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl)

DPPH radical scavenging activity was determined as recommended by Sharma and Bhat [22]. A 2 mM 2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (Sigma-Aldrich, Cat. D9132) methanol solution was prepared and diluted 1:10 in 70% ethanol. Samples were dissolved in either MQW or 70% ethanol, prepared in triplicate and in 4 to 5 concentrations. On a microplate (Thermo NUNC, Cat. 269620, Germany), a 150 µL sample was mixed with 50 µL of 0.2 mM DPPH or 70% ethanol solution, for control. The blank was 150 µL of sample solvent and 50 µL of DPPH and a control blank consisted of 150 µL of sample solvent and 50 µL of 70% ethanol. The plate was shaken for 30 min at 320 Mot/1 min, protected from light (IKA® KS 130 basic), and absorbance was measured at 520 nm (Multiskan Sky, Thermo Fisher). The control sample, blank, and control blank were used to remove background noise and increase the inter- and intra-accuracy of the assay. DPPH logarithmic curves were generated from concentration vs. percent radical inhibition plots and used to calculate the IC₅₀ values in mg/mL ± standard error of the mean (SEM). Results expressed as IC₅₀ values (mg/mL) were compiled from one run, with every extract run in five concentrations and each concentration in triplicate.

ORAC

Oxygen radical absorbance capacity (ORAC) assay was conducted as recommended by Ganske and Dell [23] and Huang et al. [24]. A 10 nM fluorescein solution was prepared with a 10 mM phosphate buffer. Blanks were made with the sample solvent, consisting of 70% ethanol. The standards were made from Trolox diluted in methanol and 10 mM phosphate buffer. The plate was incubated for 10 min at 37°C and then run for 100 cycles with adding 2,2'-Azobis(2-amidinopropane) dihydrochloride (AAPH) throughout the cycles. The fluorescence was measured at an excitation at 484 nm and emission at 520 nm on a Polarstar spectrophotometer, Optima, BMG Labtech. The ORAC value was then calculated by the area under the curve (AUC) over the 100 cycles. The net AUC is obtained by subtracting the AUC of the blank from that of a sample or standard. The ORAC value is calculated and expressed as micromoles of Trolox equivalents per gram (μmol of TE/g).

Reducing power

Reducing power assay was conducted according to Oyaizu [25] and Apak et al. [26] A 0.2 M phosphate buffer (pH 6.6) was made as well as a 1% potassium ferricyanide ($\text{K}_3\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$) solution, 0.1% ferric chloride and 10% trichloroacetic acid (CCl_3COOH). For standard L-ascorbic acid calibration solutions were prepared. On a microplate (Thermo NUNC, Cat. 269620, Germany), 13 μL of standard or samples were added with 63 μL of the phosphate buffer and 63 μL of potassium ferricyanide solution. The microplate was incubated at 50°C for 30 min before adding 63 μL of TCA and 40 μL of ferric chloride (FeCl_3). The absorbance was measured at 720 nm on a Multi-scan Sky Spectrophotometer, Thermo Fisher Scientific. The reducing power was expressed as micromoles of ascorbic acid equivalents per gram.

Metal chelating

Metal chelating (MC) assay was conducted according to Stookey et al. [27] and Boyer et al. [28] Both 0.2 mM ferrous chloride and 0.5mM ferrozine solutions were prepared. In a microplate (Thermo NUNC, Cat. 269620, Germany), 100 μL of sample solvent (water and 70% ethanol) or sample were mixed with 50 μL of ferrous chloride and either 100 μL of water or 100 μL of ferrozine. The microplate was shaken for 30 min at room temperature before being analysed at 560 nm. MC logarithmic curves were generated from concentration vs. percent radical

inhibition plots and used to calculate the IC₅₀ values in mg/mL ±standard error of the mean (SEM). Results expressed as IC₅₀ values (mg/mL) were compiled from one run, with every extract run in four to five concentrations and each concentration in triplicate.

Statistical analysis

The difference between the antioxidant results was compared by Kruskal Wallis followed by Dunn *post-hoc* test adjusted by Bonferroni for multiple comparisons. The statistical analysis was carried out on R version 4.5.1 with the packages `dunn.test`, `multicompview` and `tidyverse` (R-project, Vienna, Austria).

Results and Discussion

Different fractions were extracted from Icelandic *A. nodosum* by applying a sequential extraction protocol developed for full utilisation of the biomass. The process is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Sequential extraction procedure from *A. nodosum*

The procedure is detailed in the processing protocol in Appendix 1. Here below are pictures demonstrating the procedure.

Biostimulant extraction

Fucoxanthin extraction

<p>Seaweed residue + 70% ethanol for fucoxanthin extraction</p>	<p>Fucoxanthin extract and residue biomass dried.</p>	<p>Fucoxanthin extracts: 3 mm wet, dried at 55 and 70°C</p>

Alginate extraction

<p>Residue treated with 0.1M and 0.2M HCl</p>	<p>Alginate filtrate liquids</p>	<p>Alginate precipitated with ethanol</p>
<p>Alginate filtered out and cleaned with acetone</p>	<p>Dried alginate</p>	<p>Alginate re-dissolved in water</p>

Cellulose fraction

Cellulose extraction with sodium chlorite	Cellulose rinsed at neutral pH	Cellulose rinsed at neutral pH
Post alginate extraction treated (treated with HCl at left 0.2M, right 0.1M)	Cellulose extraction with H ₂ O ₂ heated at 80°C for 5h	Cellulose fraction residue collected after filtration

This sequential extraction process is allowing a full utilisation of *A. nodosum* as after the cellulose extraction, no by-product is left behind. As the aim of this project was to find other products that could be created to valorise the residue present after the biostimulant extraction, this sequential extraction has allowed the project to reach its goal. The next steps would be developing greener processes to improve this sequential extraction while not compromising the purity of the products. Each step will still need more specific improvements, mainly when full scale-up will be designed as adjustments will need to be done.

Extract yields

Biostimulants

As numerous extractions were conducted both at laboratory scale and scale-up, different extract yields were recorded. During the tests done at laboratory scale (see Table 1) the following extract yields were found for biostimulant:

Process used	Extract yield (on a dry basis)
1:5	32%
1:10 1 sec on/2 sec off for 5 min	30%
1:10 15 min on	31%

During scale up (see Table 2), the yields from each extraction of biostimulant were the following:

Particle size and time	Extract yield (on a dry basis)
<0.25 mm – 20 min	36%
0.8-2 mm – 10 min	22%
0.8-2 mm – 20 min	24%
3 mm – 1 h	30%

The higher yield of biostimulant observed when the seaweed particles were <0.25 mm was due to the finer particles eluting through the 50 µm filter, resulting in more seaweed particles in the biostimulant. This may increase the antioxidant properties of the biostimulant [29]. During the scale-up and using bigger volumes of water and dry biomass, it was clear that running the ultrasound for a longer time allowed for better extraction yield.

Fucoxanthin extract

Fucoxanthin was extracted from several different samples using 70% ethanol and different extraction methods. The yield of fucoxanthin extract was around 17% as can be seen below:

Process used	Extract yield (on a dry basis)
<0.25 mm – 20 min	16.9%
0.8-2 mm - 20 min bath extract	17.1%
0.8-2 mm – 20 min probe extract	16.8%
3 mm – 1 h – wet	17.4%
3 mm – 1 h dried at 55°C*	5.7%
3 mm – 1 h dried at 70°C*	5.2%

*Drying of the seaweed residue (3 mm particle size) after biostimulant extraction was tested at 55°C and 70°C. A third part of the seaweed residue material (3 mm particle size) was kept wet. Fucoxanthin was then extracted from the 3 residues, using 70% ethanol. As can be seen here above drying of the seaweed residue material gave a lower fucoxanthin extract yield. There is also a visible colour difference between the extracts (Figure 2). It has been shown before that fucoxanthin is sensitive to heat and that already at 60°C it degrades significantly [30]. This analysis showed that even at 55°C, most of the fucoxanthin in the sample was already degraded.

Figure 2: Fucoxanthin extracts from 3 mm size particle, in 70% EtOH post sonication; Left to right: wet, dried at 55°C and dried at 70°C.

Fucoidan, Alginate and cellulose

When the sodium chlorite-based cellulose extraction method used was the one with, a clear (white) cellulose was obtained with a yield of 11%. In contrast, when a greener extraction method (H_2O_2), and different acid concentration during fucoidan extraction, the final material was still green (not fully bleached cellulose), and the yields were higher, respectively 21% when the raw material was treated during fucoidan extraction with 0.1M HCl and 34% when it was treated with 0.2M HCl.

Overall, the different extractions both at laboratory scale and during a scale up show the following extraction yields:

- Biostimulant: between 22% and 36%,
- Fucoxanthin extract: between 12% and 17.4%,
- Fucoidans: 7%,
- Alginates: 24%
- Cellulose fraction: between 11% (clean), 21% (some impurities) and 34% (a lot of impurities).

This show that by doing sequential extraction of *A. nodosum*, between 76% and 95% can be recovered in numerous products, where each can be used in specific processes.

Characterisation of each product

Biostimulant

The water content and dry matter content of all the biostimulant liquids and seaweed residue material after biostimulant extraction were recorded. Moreover, the total polyphenol content, and other antioxidant properties were determined (described in the antioxidant section). Table 3 summarises the dry matter content of each part:

Table 3. Dry matter content of the biostimulants extracted with different methods from different raw materials, with different particle size.

Sample	Dry matter content (%) in the biostimulant
Laboratory scale: 1:5	6.9%
Laboratory scale: 1:10-5 min	3.6%
Laboratory scale: 1:10-15 min	3.8%
Scale -up: <0.25 mm	5.6%
Scale -up: 0.8-2 mm 10 min	3.4%
Scale -up: 0.8-2 mm – 20 min	3.6%
Scale -up: 3 mm -1 h	4.0%

Smaller particle size gave higher dry matter content in the biostimulant due to the filter mesh size, which allows for higher particle content in the biostimulant. Dry matter is however not the important parameter, but the content of the biostimulating compounds, e.g., polysaccharides and polyphenols [31].

Fucoxanthin

An HPLC method was set up at Matis to determine the fucoxanthin concentration in several extracts and the biostimulant. As can be seen from Figure 3A, the biostimulant did not contain any fucoxanthin, this was also the case for the alginate residue liquid. The fucoxanthin content of samples analysed can be found in Table 4.

Figure 3: HPLC chromatogram of fucoxanthin in A: biostimulant, B: fucoxanthin extract (3 mm dried @70°C), C: fucoxanthin extract (3 mm dried @ 55°C) and D: fucoxanthin extract (3 mm wet).

Table 4. Fucoxanthin content (mg/g) in different extracts. LOD: Limit of Detection.

Sample	mg fucoxanthin / g extract
Biostimulant <0.25	<LOD
Biostimulant 3mm 1h	<LOD
Alginate rest liquid	<LOD
Fucoxanthin <0.25 probe	0.1
Fucoxanthin 0.8-2.5mm probe	0.2
Fucoxanthin 0,8-2,5mm bath	0.2
55°C	0.2
70°C	0.1
0.25-K	0.1
3mm wet	0.9

Fucoidan content

The fucoidan content was analysed in the fucoidan extracted with 0.1M HCl (F1) and with 0.2M HCl (F2). Figure 4 shows the chromatogram of F1. Fucose is the basic sugar in fucoidan, but sulphate groups (which are heavy) and other side groups still need to be considered when estimating the amount of the polysaccharide. This varies between species, and if no complementary data is available, it can generally be assumed an approximate 2x fucose to calculate the amount of fucoidan. In Table 5, the fucose content of F1 and F2 is 13%, this would mean that ~26% of the dry matter is fucoidan.

Figure 4: HPAE-PAD chromatogram of fucoidan extract F1. Containing mainly fucose, but also some xylose or mannose (peaks co-elute).

Salt content

The fucoidan extracts, were dried and analysed for salt content to evaluate, from the dry matter content, how much salt was present due to the extraction process (reaction of HCl with NaOH). The fucoidan extracted with 0.1M HCl (**F1**) had a salt content of 37.8% ($\pm 11\%$) and the extract treated with 0.2M HCl (**F2**) had a salt content of 44% ($\pm 11\%$).

Protein content

The protein content was measured in 4 samples, F2, Alginate residue, cellulose fractions 0.1M and 0.2M the extracts treated with 0.1M and 0.2M HCl had respectively 0.3% and 0.2% protein residue in them.

Alginate and cellulose

The alginate, once dried, was rehydrated, to verify that a gel was forming. When a ratio of around 1:5 sample water was used, the jellification process started directly, confirming a successful extraction of alginates. The alginate content of the extract was further investigated and confirmed by monosaccharide analysis.

For cellulose, when the sodium chlorite method was used, the extract had a similar appearance as in previous tests done, so no further tests were performed. However, when the greener method was used, as the extracts had a green colour, they were analysed for dry matter content, and the cellulose coming from the rest biomass from alginate extraction with 0.1M and 0.2M HCl had respectively, 1.52 and 1.79% of dry matter. As they looked like forming a gel, it showed that the process had started to work but was probably not fully completed.

Monosaccharide composition

There is no alginate in A1-3 (alginate rest liquid) and fucose is <1%, which is below the standard. High amounts of alginate in A4 (alginate product) and some fuc and xyl (not glucose like in the purchased alginic acid). The Fuc 95% standard seems fairly pure, although the sulphate side groups still need to be considered. The purchased alginic acid standard has ~34% alginate and >50% glucose, which is unusual. The result for the Cellulose sample is inaccurate because of low dry matter. Results were divided by 0.014 to get as a percentage of dry matter. The sample was injected undiluted but was still below standard. Reference standards for the monosaccharides were mannitol, fucose, galactose, glucose and xylose. Reference standards for uronic acids were guluronic acid and mannuronic acid.

Table 5. Monosaccharide composition in percentage of extract/sample. Fuc \geq 95% = Fucoidan from *Fucus vesiculosus* \geq 95% from Sigma-Aldrich, F8190. Alg acid = Alginic acid sodium salt from Sigma-Aldrich, 180947. F1 = Fucoidan 0.1M, F2 = Fucoidan 0.2M.

Sample	Mannitol	Fuc	Gal	Gluc	Xyl	Mannur	Guluron	M+G	M/G
Fuc \geq 95%		33.7%	2.2%		5%			<3%	
Alg acid				55%		21.1%	12.4%	34%	1.7%
A1		<0,7%			Low				
A2		<1%			Low				
A3		<0,5%			Low				
A4		4.7%			3.5%	32%	18%	50%	1.8%
F1	1.4%	13.1%	0.3%	2%	2.6%				
F2	0.8%	13.3%	0.3%	1.3%	2.5%				
Cellulose		9.7%		11.8%	2.2%	8%	4%	12%	2%

Antioxidant activity

Since polyphenols are considered to be biostimulating compounds, it was decided to investigate the total polyphenol content (TPC) in the biostimulant as well as the fucoxanthin and fucoïdan extracts. As can be seen from Table 6 there are some polyphenols in the biostimulant. Polyphenols are also found in the fucoïdan extracts, although less than in the biostimulant, which is to be expected. Since polyphenolic compounds are usually more soluble in less polar solvents than water, 70% ethanol was used to extract fucoxanthin, and the highest TPC was found in the fucoxanthin extracts. It can however be seen from the results (Table 6) that samples dried at higher temperatures had lower TPC, suggesting that increased temperature degrades polyphenolic compounds. Significant reduction in TPC and antioxidant activity with increasing drying temperatures has been demonstrated before [32].

The raw material particle size also seems to affect the TPC, as a lower TPC was found for the 3 mm particle size extracts. A seasonal variation can however not be excluded here, since the 3 mm material was harvested in July 2025. Seasonal variation in TPC is well known for seaweed [33, 34]. Moreover, extraction in ultrasound bath at 45°C seem to result in slightly higher TPC compared to the ultrasound probe, which might be explained both by the slightly higher temperature and the larger surface of the sample treated during extraction. However, as the use of the ultrasound probe has not yet been optimised, the results could be similar once the parameters and the process will be optimised.

Fucoxanthin is a known potent antioxidant, which can be seen from the high ORAC values and low DPPH results of the fucoxanthin extracts in Table 6. Noviendri et al. [35] found high TPC and antioxidant activity of ethanolic fucoxanthin extracts from Indonesian brown seaweeds (*Padina* sp., *Turbinaria* sp., *Sargassum* sp.). The fucoxanthin content of the Indonesian extracts were similar or lower than for the Icelandic fucoxanthin extract from *A. nodosum* investigated herein. Different extracts from Icelandic *A. nodosum* have been analysed for antioxidant properties before and demonstrated high antioxidant activities as demonstrated in this study [36].

The main conclusion from the antioxidant analysis is that heating of the residue material to dry them, negatively affects the antioxidant activity of the resulting extracts.

Table 6. Results are shown as mean values ($n = 9$) \pm standard deviation (SD). Different letters within a column indicate a statistically significant difference ($p < 0.05$). TPC = Total polyphenol content, PG = Phloroglucinol, GA = Gallic acid, AA = L-ascorbic acid, RP = Reducing power, MC = Metal chelating. The high standard deviation in fucoxanthin extracts is most probably linked to different water content from the extracts.

Sample	TPC g GA eq/100g	TPC g PG eq/100g	RP mg AA eq/g	ORAC μ mol TE eq/g	DPPH IC ₅₀ (mg/ml)	MC IC ₅₀ (mg/ml)
Biostimulant <0.25	5.2 ^{abc} \pm 0.6	6.6 ^{abc} \pm 0.9	0.07 ^{abcd} \pm 0.0			0.35 ^{abc} \pm 0.05
Biostim 0.8-2.5mm 10min	3.3 ^{abc} \pm 0.3	4.2 ^{ab} \pm 0.4	0.03 ^{abc} \pm 0.0			0.48 ^{ab} \pm 0.17
Biostim 0.8-2.5mm 20min	3.9 ^{abc} \pm 0.5	4.7 ^{abc} \pm 0.8	0.04 ^{abcd} \pm 0.0			0.17 ^c \pm 0.12
Biostim 3mm 1h	4.1 ^{abc} \pm 1.4	5.0 ^{abc} \pm 0.8	0.03 ^{abcd} \pm 0.0			0.22 ^{ac} \pm 0.09
Fucoxanthin <0.25 probe	18 ^c \pm 1.0	23 ^{bc} \pm 4.1	0.21 ^{bcd} \pm 0.1	1500 ^{ac} \pm 370	0.021 ^{ab} \pm 0.013	
Fucoxanthin 0.8-2.5mm probe	15 ^{bc} \pm 2.9	19 ^{bc} \pm 2.6	0.27 ^{cd} \pm 0.0	1530 ^{ac} \pm 600	0.008 ^a \pm 0.001	
Fucoxanthin 0,8-2,5mm bath	21 ^c \pm 2.7	27 ^c \pm 3.5	0.41 ^d \pm 0.1	1650 ^a \pm 450	0.005 ^a \pm 0.002	
Fucoxanthin 3mm 55°C	2.3 ^a \pm 0.3	6.2 ^{abc} \pm 4.1	0.01 ^a \pm 0.0	390 ^b \pm 65	0.152 ^b \pm 0.030	
Fucoxanthin 3mm 70°C	2.7 ^{ab} \pm 0.3	3.4 ^a \pm 0.7	0.01 ^a \pm 0.0	500 ^{bc} \pm 160	0.131 ^b \pm 0.090	
Fucoxanthin 3mm wet	11 ^{bc} \pm 2.1	9.1 ^{abc} \pm 5.4	0.23 ^{bcd} \pm 0.1	1130 ^{abc} \pm 530	0.017 ^{ab} \pm 0.007	
Furoidan 0.1M	2.9 ^{ab} \pm 0.6	3.9 ^{ab} \pm 0.9	0.04 ^{abcd} \pm 0.0			0.45 ^{abc} \pm 0.16
Furoidan 0.2M	2.4 ^a \pm 0.5	3.2 ^a \pm 0.7	0.03 ^{ab} \pm 0.0			0.82 ^b \pm 0.39

Conclusions

To ensure higher yields throughout the sequential extraction and maintain high antioxidant activity in all the extracts it is necessary to keep the residue wet and so the sequential extraction as a continuous process without drying steps in between. This is ensuring that no carotenoid degradation is happening and that both yields, purity and antioxidant capacity of the sequential extracts will stay high. It is also important to ensure that neither the seaweed, nor the extracts mainly when extracting fucoxanthin will reach a temperature above 55°C (even recommended lower temperature) as the fucoxanthin and polyphenolic compounds seems to already be degrading at that temperature.

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Annex 1

Processing protocol

Biostimulant extraction

See material and methods – biostimulant extraction – page 7

Fucoxanthin extraction

1. Residue biomass from biostimulant extraction (**Residue 1 – R1** – sample name from the Experimental set-up Excel sheet).
2. Grind into fine powder if needed.
3. Weigh 4 g (16 g) of dry powder.
4. Add 500 mL (2000 mL) of 70% ethanol (final concentration if using wet residue) – mix well.
5. Sonicate for 15 min.
6. Separate **Residue 2 (R2)** from supernatant by filtration or centrifugation.
8. Evaporate solvent from supernatant until dry fucoxanthin extract.
9. Analyse for fucoxanthin content (or freeze for analyse later) (Fucoxanthin HPLC method).

Fuoidan extraction

10. Dry or wet pellet (**Residue 2 – R2**).
11. Weigh 2 g (8 g) (dry matter) into 100 mL centrifugation tube.
12. Suspend in 50 mL (200 mL) 0.2M HCl and gently shake for 2 h.
13. Separate solids (**Residue 3 – R3**) from the liquid.
14. Supernatant neutralised with NaOH, freeze dried and weighed.
15. Analyse for salt and fuoidan content. Dialysis for purer fuoidan extract.

Alginate extraction

16. **Residue 3** – homogenously re-suspend in distilled water and shake for 1 h.
17. Separate solids from liquid and discharge supernatant.
18. Resuspend pellet in 90 mL (360 mL) 0.1M NaHCO₃, gently shake for 2 h.
19. Adjust pH to 8 with NaOH.
20. Stir over night (~12 h).
21. Filter and save supernatant for alginate recovery.
22. Residue resuspended in H₂O and pH adjusted to >7.
23. Shake for 2 h.
24. Filter and save supernatant for alginate recovery.
25. Repeat extraction in H₂O (pH >7.5) 3 times.
26. Producing 4 supernatants and 1 residue (**Residue 4 – R4**).

Alginate recovery

27. Combine the 4 supernatants into one (A4), record the total volume.
28. NaCl suspended in a small volume of water and added to the supernatants, assuring 0.2% (w/v) – mix well.
29. Supernatant mixed with ethanol at 1:3 v/v ration to precipitate sodium alginate.
30. Filter out the solid alginates using a 20 µm nylon filter (possible to leave in fridge overnight).
31. Wash the solids with cold ethanol, and last acetone. Save the solvent for analysis (A1, A2, A3).
32. Alginate dried at 65°C overnight.
33. Analyse for alginate content (method).

Preparation of cellulose

34. Using dry or wet **R4** (4 g of dry material).
35. Pre-heat a water bath at 70°C.
36. Weigh 4 g of dry powder into a bottle.
37. Add 700 mL of 1.4% (w/v) NaClO₂ solution – quantities can be adapted to 8 g of powder into 700 mL of 1.4% NaClO₂ solution.
38. Adjust pH to 3 with acetic acid (add pure acetic acid, approximately 20 mL or more will be required to reach pH 3, it depends on the seaweed species).
39. Treat for 5 h at 70°C and stirring 140 rpm in a water bath (the seaweed initially float into the liquid, when it reaches the cellulose state it sinks at the bottom).
40. Stop reaction by cooling in fridge overnight.
41. Solutions should become transparent – flashy yellow with yellow solid. If it becomes yellow then you have F2A, if not then extra steps will be needed.
42. For F2A: Filter out the yellow solid and wash repeatedly with MQ water by filtrating it on a 20 µm pores nylon filter, until the liquid filtrated becomes approx. neutral (it will require around 5 L of H₂O for the initial 4 g of dry samples). OR as often some cellulose particle will pass through the filter: remove the liquid form the solid, rinse once with distilled water – set the solids into a box and until the solid become white/transparent, rinse with distilled water, once this is done, filtrate again. The pH should be around 1.2. Then, rinse the solid with 0.05M NaOH solution, and then up to 1M NaOH solution to have the pH back to around 6-7. It will take a long time, and a lot of 0.1M NaOH to reach pH 5 (approx 2 L of solution for initially 10 g of dry seaweed), once you are around pH 5, the pH will increase quickly - if the pH goes higher than 8 then the look of the cellulose gel will change – becoming transparent and yellow / state we do not want to reach). This obtains the cellulose fraction F2A.
43. Take a part of F2A to measure water content with AOAC method (oven dried).
44. For the samples that do not turn yellow, more steps are required for cellulose extraction.
45. Treat the biomass with 5% HCl until boiling and then let it cool down to room temp overnight.
46. Remove the liquid by filtrating on the 20 µm pore filter.
47. Treat the rest biomass with 400 mL 5% (w/v) KOH solution for 24 h at room temperature followed by 2 h at 90°C, in order to remove hemicellulose and yield F3A.
48. Filter through 20 µm pore filter and rinse with water until the colour of the cellulose becomes as colourless as possible (ideally transparent/white gel formed) and pH of filtrate around neutral.
49. Take a part of the cellulose (F3A) to measure the water content.